

Education Quarterly Reviews

Lin, Ch., Azar, A. S., & Ahmad, A. (2023). The Effects of Charismatic Aspects of Transformational Leadership on Personal Outcomes: An Empirical Literature Review. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 6(2), 212-220.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.06.02.750

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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The Effects of Charismatic Aspects of Transformational Leadership on Personal Outcomes: An Empirical Literature Review

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Abstract

Idealized influence, combined with inspirational motivation, constitutes the charismatic-based aspect of transformational leadership. However, few researchers examined the influence of these two traits exerting on the employee's personal outcomes in the workplace and more research should be conducted. The goal of this paper turns to identify and analyze empirical articles on the effect of the charismatic aspect of transformational leadership on personal outcomes from the year 2013 to 2022. Such online databases like Google Scholar, ERIC, Web of Science and ProQuest were used to collect the literature. Induction analysis, narrative synthesis was utilized to analyze the articles and three conclusions can be drawn: 1) A positive impact of Idealized influence and inspirational motivation on related personal outcomes like job performance, job satisfaction and the job engagement was confirmed but the impact on job performance seems having received more concerns than the influence on job satisfaction and the engagement. 2) Most of the research are conducted in countries like Kenyan, Indonesia, Yemen, Jordan. Industries mainly involved in business sector like state-owned enterprises and private businesses, so the research context should be expanded to other places and countries and include more industries. 3) Future researchers are advised to concentrate more on the influence of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on personal outcomes such as job satisfaction, job engagement, job commitment, and the explanatory mechanism need to be more creative and innovative when supporting with a new theoretical foundation.

Keywords: Idealized Influence, Inspirational Motivation, Personal Outcomes, Empirical Review

1. Introduction

Idealized influence and inspirational motivation are two important subunits of transformational leadership and were considered as the charismatic-based aspect of the transformational leadership. Just like what the majority of

transformational theorists, such as Avolio, Bass, Deluga and Howell, hold that charisma is the primary ingredient in the transformational process. Charisma is the capacity of a leader to inspire admiration. Idealized influence, accompanied by inspirational motivation, composes charisma behavior within transformational leadership (Cicero & Pierro, 2007). When leaders are good role models and have personalities that inspire followers to enthusiastically imitate their behaviors and activities, they are said to have idealized influence (Groves, 2014; Northouse, 2021). Therefore, leaders with idealized influence behaviors inspire their followers to put the team's needs before their own and go above and beyond in terms of personal sacrifice and service. While inspirational motivation is a kind of leadership that leaders will employ it to promote a sense of pride. When a follower feels inspired or touched by the leader, inspirational motivation is utilized.

There is an increasing number of research exploring the impact of transformational leadership on outcomes like OCB, task performance, organization level and personal performance. Both individual follower results (Arnold et al., 2001; Bakker et al., 2022; Kehr et al., 2022) and group/organizational outcomes (Boerner et al., 2007; Purwanto et al., 2021; WANASIDA et al., 2021) have been linked to transformational leadership. And the capacity of a transformation leader is also confirmed to have effect on satisfaction of followers (Allozi et al., 2022; Bushra et al., 2011) and dedication (Chen & Cuervo, 2022) to the organization. Additionally, employee's self-motivation and commitment to organizational change and organizational conditions (Adnan & Azar, 2023; Herold et al., 2008; Ramos-Maçães & Román-Portas, 2022) are also affected by transformational leadership. Organizations of any kind require transformational leadership because it can positively affect success of the individual and the organization (Sharma & Jain, 2022). There is accumulating evidence demonstrating that transformational leadership is associated with positive outcomes like increased individual and collective efficacy of teachers (Gkolia et al., 2018; Windlinger et al., 2020); increased organizational citizenship behavior (Handayani, 2018); increased employee well-being (Donohoe & Kelloway, 2016; Kelloway et al., 2012; Sharifirad, 2013). But when we key idealized influence, inspirational motivation, charisma, and charismatic with the words of leader, leadership, and follower, by using key terms, titles, and abstracts to search databases like Papers First, Google Scholar, ProQuest Dissertations and Theses, and the Web of science to search for the related research as to their impact on employees' personal outcomes. The research is comparatively inadequate than transformational leadership and further specific research on these two dimensions should be carried out.

This literature review aims to identify and classify the recent literatures on how this charismatic aspect of transformational leadership predicts the personal outcomes, to draw literature-based conclusions and then the direction for future study is also figured out.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Idealized Influence

Idealized influence, meaning being influential about ideals, encompasses influence both over ideology and “bigger-than-life” issues, is the very first dimension of transformational leadership (Avolio et al., 1991). It refers to a transformational leader's capacity of exhibiting themselves as role models, high levels of idealized influence can enhance subordinates' confidence and respect in leaders (Eberly et al., 2017; Money, 2017). Ogola et al. (2017) figured out that transformational leaders with high degrees of idealized influence inspire followers' admiration and dedication. Idealized influence promotes a follower's desire to imitate a leader, allowing the leader to socialize with the followers. Bodla and Nawaz (2010) identified two perspectives of idealized influence: leaders' actions and those aspects of the leader's personality that are associated with the leader's supporters. Similarly, Loon et al. (2012) investigated idealized influence from a more detail aspect through two elements: “idealized influence-attributed” and “idealized influence-behavior”. While “idealized influence-behavior” is understood as the specific behavior of leaders, “idealized influence attribution” relates to how followers and/or employees perceive and consequently experience leaders. Leaders with idealized influence possesses the qualities of being strong, charismatic, and self-assured and these qualities can be felt by their subordinates (Aydogdu & Asikgil, 2011).

According to Sosik and Godshalk (2000), idealized influence is a necessary and laudable quality in a leader. Such leaders are often held up as examples to follow or entrusted with coaching responsibilities. When acting as a role

model, characteristics of idealized influence are exhibiting and the followers are inspired to achieve goals, and the subordinates are encouraged to get involved to advance their careers (Sorkin & Rook, 2004).

2.2 Inspirational Motivation

“Although inspirational motivation has been seen as an essential ingredient of transformational leadership”(Rafferty & Griffin, 2004), this concept has been conceptualized in a variety of ways. According to Bass and Bass Bernard (1985), charismatic leaders encourage the people they lead to prioritize the organization's needs over their own through a combination of inspirational words and emotional appeals. The use of emotional components and emotional appeals in the workplace is a key part of the process by which inspirational leadership impacts employees. Later in 1999, Bass confirmed that a leader possesses charisma and inspirational motivation when they foresee the future, plan for its realization, set an exemplary example, demand excellent performance, and demonstrate conviction. According to Downton (1973), inspirational motivation is the capacity to evoke thought and feeling. There is a similar idea proposed by Keskes (2014) that the meaning of “inspiration” refers to the degree that a leader stimulates enthusiasm amongst their subordinates and the words they say to build confidence in subordinates in their ability and then perform better to accomplish assignments successfully and attain group objectives.

Superior performance outcomes are associated with higher levels of staff engagement and effectiveness, both of which are the direct result of a leader's use of inspirational motivation, a recognized contributor to employee dedication(Gallup, 2017). Leaders appeal to their followers' sense of inspiration to win them over and secure their backing for a plan of action or desired outcome. Motivating leaders encouraged their teams to think about the bigger picture and how their efforts could make a difference (Bass & Riggio, 2006). By mutual communication of fresh ideas, leaders with inspirational motivation behavior win enthusiastic supporters and the devoted supporters also accept leader's idea with grace and optimism (Bass, 2008). When devotees realized the rationale behind their devotion, they could better see the big picture and were more likely to give their all to the cause thus being more engaged. Employees may have more confidence in their leaders and their ways of leadership if leaders are able to communicate effectively with their subordinates and form close bonds with them. By articulating organization's future vision, leaders can enable employees understand the organizational goal better and accept it willingly thus can motivate them to work devotedly to achieve the goal (Podsakoff et al., 1990). The combination of these characteristics can strengthen workers' commitment to the company, which in turn will boost their job satisfaction and productivity.

2.3 An Empirical Literature Review of the Charismatic Perspectives of Transformational Leadership

There is a large number of research papers related to transformational leadership constructs, nonetheless, the literature often fails to adequately explore the specific facets of the construct and lead to a limiting clarity of how the dimensions impact organizations(Kariuki, 2021). A key aspect of transformational leadership is charisma, which manifests itself in the form of idealized influence and inspirational motivation. Studies are identified when we search for these two factors in google scholar and ProQuest to learn more about their effect on the engagement of employees.

Sahibzada et al. (2016) looked at how leaders' idealized influence and inspirational motivation affected workers' happiness, namely job satisfaction at the workplace. A well-established questionnaire survey was conducted among 330 employees from ten different private universities in KPK to explore the connection between the idealized influence, inspirational motivation and employee satisfaction in the job. It is found that both of these two variables exert significant impact on employee's job satisfaction. The study produced significant findings that will result in behavioral improvements in the education sector's leadership style, which will eventually increase employee job satisfaction levels.

Different from the research of Sahibzada et al. (2016) on job satisfaction of employees, Ngaithe et al. (2016) utilized these charismatic traits of idealized influence and inspirational motivation to delve into the influence of these trait factors on the productivity of employees at Kenyan state-owned businesses. It is concluded in the

research that these two traits of transformational leadership increased employee's performance in Kenyan State-owned businesses positively and significantly.

Also in Kenyan, the study of Nyokabi et al. (2017) was to determine the impact of Kenyan CEO's charismatic leadership traits on the performance of the senior managers in private businesses. It was discovered that both CEO's idealized influence and CEO's inspiring motivation were found to be significant predictors of senior manager performance in a multiple linear regression analysis. What's more, as a moderator, goal orientation was also tested and found that it significantly moderates the relationship between the idealized influence, inspirational motivation and senior managers' performance.

Applying only dimension of idealized influence, Change et al. (2019) investigated the impact of idealized influence having on employee engagement in energy sectors in Kenya. This research also aimed to determine how inspirational motivation impacts the link between idealized influence and staff engagement. Statistical analysis shows a strong correlation between employee engagement and charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork.

Low-level managers across Kenyan insurance companies were invited to participated in quantitative research by Langat (2019a) to analyze the link between transformation leadership and employee performance, with a focus on the moderating role played by employee work value congruence. According to the results of the study, idealized influence is a strong predictor of workers' actual performance on the job. Results also showed that among lower-level managers in Kenya's insurance industry, work value congruence significantly moderated the connection between transformational leadership and employee job performance.

Collecting information from two manufacturing groups in Australia and Iran. Afshari (2021) seeks to understand the connections between the idealized impact aspect of transformational leadership and employee organizational commitment in two distinct cultural settings. Based on the analysis, two idealized influence dimensions (attributed and behavioral) were found to be significantly associated with organizational commitment among workers in Iranian sample. Among the Australian sample, however, only idealized influence behavior was found to significantly affect employee commitment. Another key conclusion was drawn that identified motivation acts as a positive mediator between idealized influence behavior and organizational commitment.

Also specific in dimensions, Le and Le (2021) investigate the link between knowledge sharing (KS) and the innovation performance of businesses by focusing on the role of idealized influence and inspiring motivation. The results demonstrate the importance of employee KS activities in enhancing business innovation performance and as a moderator in the impacts of TL on innovation performance. Furthermore, comparing the effect of idealized influence and the effect of individualized consideration on innovation performance, the latter is found to be more significant.

In a research by Alzoraiki et al. (2018), researching goal was to investigate how different aspects of transformational leadership affect teachers' classroom performance in public schools in Yemen. A total of 374 respondents including staff and teachers were chosen as the sample to get responses and positive effects on teacher performance were observed across all these four dimensions of transformational leadership.

Using a quantitative research design, according to research conducted by Sutanto et al. (2021) in Indonesia, who examined the effects of all four dimensions of transformational leadership on HR performance, it is found that inspirational motivation, individual consideration, and intellectual stimulation all have a positive and significant effect on HR performance. HR performance is also positively related to idealized influence. However, this correlation is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant.

Using transformational leadership and perspective theory, ALmahasneh et al. (2022) studied the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on the culture of the organization in Jordanian information businesses. Using a quantitative design, data were gathered from the managers at three levels, the results indicate that idealized influence and inspirational motivation have a constructive effect on the culture of an organization.

Culture in the workplace has a mediation effect on the dynamics between idealized influence and organizational performance, and inspirational motivation and organizational performance as well.

In order to have a clearer picture of these empirical studies, a matrix table of these two factors is made as follow:

Table 1: The Present Study of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on Personal Outcomes

Personal outcomes	Methodology	Research context	Authors and years	Findings
Employee job satisfaction	Quantitative	Pakistan private universities	Sahibzada et al. (2016)	Non-zero relationship is found
Staff performance	Quantitative	Kenyan state-Owned Enterprises	(Ngaithe et al., 2016)	Staff performance can be predicted significantly by inspirational motivation
Performance of senior managers	Quantitative	Kenyan private businesses	Nyokabi et al. (2017)	Can predict CEO's performance significantly
Employee engagement	Quantitative	Kenyan parastatals	Change et al. (2019)	Statistically significant effect
Employee job performance	Quantitative	Insurance companies in Kenyan	Langat et al. (2019b)	A positive effect exists
Employee organizational commitment	Quantitative Comparative Research	Manufacturing organizations in Australia and Iran	(Afshari, 2021)	Having a positive effect
Knowledge sharing innovation performance	Quantitative	Firms in Vietnam	(Le & Le, 2021)	Idealized influence brings motivation to knowledge sharing
Teacher performance	Quantitative	Yemeni public schools	Alzoraiki et al. (2018)	A positive effect exists
HR performance	Quantitative	Indonesia	Sutanto et al. (2021)	A Positive and noteworthy effect exists

Bank employee's performance	Quantitative	Tanzania	Magasi (2020)	The effect is significantly positive
Bank employee's performance	Quantitative	Sub-Saharan countries	(Magasi, 2022)	The effect is significantly positive

3 Discussion

The above review summarizes the findings of the current study on the effects of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on individual outcomes like job performance, organizational commitment and satisfaction. The chosen research methodology is quantitative, and the research context focuses primarily on business sectors. And the following sector will present some discussions in detail.

Firstly, although research on transformational leadership does exist, study digging into the specific aspects of transformational leadership did not begin until a very late stage in comparison with research on transformational leadership conducted over the course of the past four decades and has only recently begun.

Secondly, the employee's performance is the main concern of researches when considering the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation, examples like performance of the staff (Ngaithe et al., 2016), manager performance (Nyokabi et al., 2017), work performance of employees (Langat et al., 2019a), knowledge sharing innovation performance (Le & Le, 2021), teacher performance (Alzoraiki et al., 2018), HR performance (Sutanto et al., 2021) well supported the idea. Only few literature explored their impact on other aspects, such as employees' job satisfactions (Sahibzada et al., 2016) and employees' engagement (Change et al., 2019).

The third point figures out that most of these researches is conducted in few countries like Kenyan, Indonesia, Yemen, Jordan. The industries involved only in some state-owned enterprises and some private sectors, some non-business organizations like universities and schools at all levels are not covered, so the research context should be expanded to other places and countries and include more industries.

Fourthly, the above-mentioned empirical literature shares the common of lacking a new theoretical explanatory angle. They share a similar conceptual framework, with an emphasis on evaluating whether or not assumptions regarding the connection between idealized influence, inspirational motivation, and individual outcomes are valid.

Finally, very few of these new studies have looked into the mediating role that exists between idealized influence, inspiring motivation and the dependent variables such as performance, satisfaction, and engagement.

Based on the above discussion, the future researchers are suggested to focus more on the influence of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on the personal outcomes like job satisfaction and job engagement or job commitment and the explanatory mechanism needs to be creative and innovative when supporting by new theoretical basis. And more research from various regions and countries is encouraged to investigate the correlations between this charismatic aspect of transformational leadership and personal outcomes.

4 Conclusion

In this empirical review, the recent literature related to the effect of the charismatic aspect of transformational leadership have been sorted out and analyzed. It is well literature-supported that positive effects on employee outcomes are greatly enhanced by idealized influence and inspirational motivation and this significant impact of transformational leadership is highlighted. However, when considering the research theoretical basis, research

context and research design, the gaps in the empirical study on influencing components of transformational leadership, namely, idealized influence and inspirational motivation, can be filled by expanding supported theory, research context and research design.

References

- Adnan, E. J., & Azar, A. S. (2023). The Impact of Self-motivation on the Effective Job Performance of Staff: A Case Study of a Private Hospital in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 6 (2), 11-28. <https://doi.org/10.31014/aior.1993.06.02.734>
- Afshari, L. (2021). Idealized influence and commitment: A granular approach in understanding leadership. *Personnel Review*.
- Allozi, A., Alshurideh, M., AlHamad, A., & Al Kurdi, B. (2022). Impact of transformational leadership on the job satisfaction with the moderating role of organizational commitment: case of UAE and Jordan manufacturing companies. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 21, 1-13.
- ALmahasneh, Y. A. S., Rahman, M. S. B., & Omar, K. B. (2022). IDEALIZED INFLUENCE, INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION, ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCES. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 57(1).
- Alzoraiki, M., Rahman, O. b. A., & Mutalib, M. A. (2018). The effect of the dimensions of transformational leadership on the teachers' performance in the Yemeni public schools. *European Scientific Journal*.
- Arnold, K. A., Barling, J., & Kelloway, E. K. (2001). Transformational leadership or the iron cage: which predicts trust, commitment and team efficacy? *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22(7), 315-320.
- Avolio, B. J., Yammarino, F. J., & Bass, B. M. (1991). Identifying common methods variance with data collected from a single source: An unresolved sticky issue. *Journal of management*, 17(3), 571-587.
- Aydogdu, S., & Asikgil, B. (2011). The effect of transformational leadership behavior on organizational culture: An application in pharmaceutical industry. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 1(4), 65-73.
- Bakker, A. B., Hetland, J., Olsen, O. K., & Espevik, R. (2022). Daily transformational leadership: A source of inspiration for follower performance? *European Management Journal*.
- Bass, B. M., & Bass Bernard, M. (1985). Leadership and performance beyond expectations.
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). Transformational leadership. *Psychology press*.
- Bodla, M. A., & Nawaz, M. M. (2010). Transformational leadership style and its relationship with satisfaction. *Interdisciplinary journal of contemporary research in business*, 2(1), 370-381.
- Boerner, S., Eisenbeiss, S. A., & Griesser, D. (2007). Follower behavior and organizational performance: The impact of transformational leaders. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 13(3), 15-26.
- Bushra, F., Ahmad, U., & Naveed, A. (2011). Effect of transformational leadership on employees' job satisfaction and organizational commitment in banking sector of Lahore (Pakistan). *International journal of Business and Social science*, 2(18).
- Change, D., Linge, T. K., & Sikalieh, D. (2019). Influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 8(5), 123-135.
- Chen, S., & Cuervo, J. C. (2022). The influence of transformational leadership on work engagement in the context of learning organization mediated by employees' motivation. *The Learning Organization*(ahead-of-print).
- Cicero, L., & Pierro, A. (2007). Charismatic leadership and organizational outcomes: The mediating role of employees' work-group identification. *International Journal of Psychology*, 42(5), 297-306.
- Donohoe, M., & Kelloway, E. K. (2016). Transformational leadership training for managers: Effects on employee well-being. In *Creating healthy workplaces* (pp. 205-221). Routledge.
- Downton, J. V. (1973). *Rebel leadership: Commitment and charisma in the revolutionary process*. Free Press.
- Eberly, M. B., Bluhm, D. J., Guarana, C., Avolio, B. J., & Hannah, S. T. (2017). Staying after the storm: How transformational leadership relates to follower turnover intentions in extreme contexts. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 102, 72-85.
- Gallup. (2017). <http://www.gallup.com/services/190118/engaged-workplace.aspx>.
- Gkolia, A., Koustelios, A., & Belias, D. (2018). Exploring the association between transformational leadership and teacher's self-efficacy in Greek education system: A multilevel SEM model. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 21(2), 176-196.
- Groves, K. S. (2014). Examining leader-follower congruence of social responsibility values in transformational leadership. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 21(3), 227-243.
- Handayani, N. P. (2018). Transformational leadership and employee engagement as a determinant of organizational citizenship behavior: Case study on youth non-profit organization. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 8(2), 59-64.

- Herold, D. M., Fedor, D. B., Caldwell, S., & Liu, Y. (2008). The effects of transformational and change leadership on employees' commitment to a change: a multilevel study. *Journal of applied psychology*, 93(2), 346.
- Kariuki, J. K. (2021). Idealized influence and inspirational motivation in a microfinance context: *Review of literature*.
- Kehr, H. M., Graff, D., & Bakaç, C. (2022). Followers' Motives as Moderators of the Effects of Transformational Leadership Behaviors on Follower Outcomes and Leaders' Influence. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 1-22.
- Kelloway, E. K., Turner, N., Barling, J., & Loughlin, C. (2012). Transformational leadership and employee psychological well-being: The mediating role of employee trust in leadership. *Work & stress*, 26(1), 39-55.
- Keskes, I. (2014). Relationship between leadership styles and dimensions of employee organizational commitment: A critical review and discussion of future directions. *Intangible Capital*, 10(1), 26-51.
- Langat, G. K., Linge, T. K., & Sikalieh, D. (2019a). Influence of idealized influence on employee job performance in the insurance industry in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 8(5), 266-273.
- Langat, G. K., Linge, T. K., & Sikalieh, D. (2019b). Influence of inspirational motivation on employee job performance in the insurance industry in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 8(6), 1-7.
- Le, L. T. K., & Le, P. B. (2021). Improving the Innovation Performance for Vietnamese Firm Based on Practices of Idealized Influence and Individualized Consideration: The Mediating Role of Knowledge Sharing. *International Journal of Business Administration*, 12(3).
- Loon, M., Lim, Y. M., Lee, T. H., & Tam, C. L. (2012). Transformational leadership and job-related learning. *Management Research Review*.
- Magasi, C. (2020). Effect of Idealised Influence and Inspirational Motivation on the Performance of the Banking Sector Employees in Dar-es-Salaam Region.
- Magasi, C. (2022). EFFECT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: A PERSPECTIVE OF LEADER'S INFLUENCE: Banking sector, employee performance, leader's influence, transformational leadership. *Business Education Journal*, 11(1).
- Money, V. (2017). Effectiveness of Transformational Leadership Style in Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(9), 135-140.
- Ngaithe, L. N., K'Aol, G. O., Lewa, P., & Ndwiga, M. (2016). Effect of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on staff performance in state owned enterprises in Kenya.
- Northouse, P. G. (2021). *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Sage publications.
- Nyokabi, S. M., K'Aol, G. O., & Njenga, K. (2017). Effect of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the CEO on performance in the private sector in Kenya.
- Ogola, M., Sikalieh, D., & Linge, T. (2017). The influence of idealized influence leadership behavior on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Moorman, R. H., & Fetter, R. (1990). Transformational leader behaviors and their effects on followers' trust in leader, satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 1(2), 107-142.
- Purwanto, A., Purba, J. T., Bernarto, I., & Sijabat, R. (2021). Effect of transformational leadership, job satisfaction, and organizational commitments on organizational citizenship behavior. *Inovbiz: Jurnal Inovasi Bisnis*, 9(1), 61-69.
- Rafferty, A. E., & Griffin, M. A. (2004). Dimensions of transformational leadership: Conceptual and empirical extensions. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 15(3), 329-354.
- Ramos-Maçães, M.-A., & Román-Portas, M. (2022). The effects of organizational communication, leadership, and employee commitment in organizational change in the hospitality sector.
- Sahibzada, S., Kakakhel, S. J., & Khan, A. (2016). Role of leaders' idealized influence and inspirational motivation on employees' job satisfaction. *University of Haripur Journal of Management (UOHJM)*, 1(2), 86-92.
- Sharifirad, M. S. (2013). Transformational leadership, innovative work behavior, and employee well-being. *Global Business Perspectives*, 1(3), 198-225.
- Sharma, P., & Jain, V. (2022). Role of culture in developing transformative leadership for higher education in emerging economies. In *Re-imagining Educational Futures in Developing Countries* (pp. 243-259). Springer.
- Sorkin, D. H., & Rook, K. S. (2004). Interpersonal control strivings and vulnerability to negative social exchanges in later life. *Psychology and Aging*, 19(4), 555.
- Sosik, J. J., & Godshalk, V. M. (2000). Leadership styles, mentoring functions received, and job-related stress: a conceptual model and preliminary study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 21(4), 365-390.
- Sutanto, H., Utami, Y., & Diantoro, A. K. (2021). The Effect of Idealized Influence, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individual Consideration on HR Performance. *RSF Conference Series: Business, Management and Social Sciences*,

- WANASIDA, A. S., BERNARTO, I., SUDIBJO, N., & PRAMONO, R. (2021). Millennial transformational leadership on organizational performance in Indonesia fishery startup. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), 555-562.
- Windlinger, R., Warwas, J., & Hostettler, U. (2020). Dual effects of transformational leadership on teacher efficacy in close and distant leadership situations. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(1), 64-87.